

DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF HYDRO-DESULPHURIZATION UNIT IN AN AMMONIA PLANT

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ABSTRACT

The research work considered the design and simulation of 200 tons per year hydro-desulphurization plant for the removal of sulfur in the form of H₂S in the cracked natural gas. The process flow diagram for the hydro-desulphurization plant consists of an absorber column and two fixed bed reactors in series aimed at absorbing the H₂S using the MDEA/H₂O as solvent and then removal of the sulphide from the absorbent through the series fixed bed reactors respectively. The models were simulated with plant data using MATLAB and Aspen HYSYS. The results from the various simulations showed that the absorber height, diameter, number and height of transfer units, and pressure drop gave values of 7.06m, 2.36m, 6 and 0.843m, and 18.43kN/m² respectively. The cost results for the absorber gave \$44,000 while cost for fixed bed reactor 1 gave \$12,000 as well as cost for fixed bed reactor 2 gave \$100,000. Finally, the models were validated with plant data and result showed that the models developed were reliable and good predictor of the process since the percentage deviations are of range 0 to 5, except H₂S component which gave 66.7 when compared the final value with the plant composition. The design results for the absorber column and the reactors gave the diameters and heights of 2.36m and 5.06m; 2.3m and 6.74m; and 1.8m and 6.74m respectively. It was observed that the pressure drop of the fixed bed reactors were 0.7bar. Simulated models performed better and reliable as the models developed predicted the process well since the results from the simulations gave good values.

Keywords: Hydro-desulphurization Unit, Natural Gas, Ammonia Plant, Design

1. INTRODUCTION

Many natural and industrial gases contain H₂S. The presence of H₂S usually prohibits the direct use of these gases because of its toxic properties, the formation of SO₂ upon combustion (acid rain), and the problems it (usually) gives in downstream processing (e.g. catalyst poisoning and corrosion of pipelines and process equipment). This means that it is often necessary to remove H₂S from the gas stream prior to use. If any CO₂ is present in the gas, simultaneous removal of CO₂ from the gas stream can occur (Nima et al., 2021).

In the past a number of processes have been developed to utilize the precipitation reaction of metal ions with sulfide. So far, the main utilization of this reaction is found in the removal of heavy metal ions from e.g. electroplating waste streams. In these cases, the primary interest was the efficient removal of metal ions from the waste stream (Ray et al., 2013).

In the regeneration step copper sulfide is oxidized to CuSO₄ in the presence of ammonium ions in a pressure vessel at a temperature of approximately 100 - 200 °C, and an oxygen partial pressure of 1.5 Bara. The product of this type of process is, apart from a cleaned-up steam flow, a concentrated stream of ammonium sulfate. The application of this process is rather limited because the process cannot

operate in a closed loop manner if under stoichiometric amounts of ammonia are present in the gas stream to be cleaned. (Maddox, 2010).

Bakhshi & Ebrahim, (2021), posited that nowadays, protecting the environment is of utmost importance worldwide, and sulfur dioxide is one of the main pollutants in the atmosphere. Their work proposed a new method for simultaneous SO₂ removal by MgO, and production of magnesium sulfate in a packed bed reactor for which breakthrough curves have been obtained.

Dushyant et al., (2004), in their study, investigated the use of activated carbon for odorant removal from natural gas to be used for synthesis gas production for fuel cells. The odorants used in their study were dimethyl sulfide, tetrahydrothiophene, methyl mercaptan, and t-butyl mercaptan.

Nawaree, (2009), defined natural gas as a mixture of variable hydrocarbons and many contain other contaminants such as nitrogen, carbon dioxide and sulfur. The undesirable compound such as hydrogen sulfide must be removed to prevent corrosion and environmental problems.

Apoorva et al., (2018), suggested that the poor quality of crude oil obviously leads to high sulfur contents of oil products, and the technology for desulfurization of crude oil is urgently needed so that the sulfur contents in petroleum product could be reduced from the root.

Ramiar & Matthaus, (2019), intimated that, Sulfur, and in particular, H₂S removal is of significant importance in gas cleaning processes in different applications, including biogas production and biomass gasification. H₂S removal with metal oxides is one of the most viable alternatives to achieve deep desulfurization. This process is usually conducted in a packed bed configuration in order to provide a high solid surface area in contact with the gas stream per unit of volume.

Zhang et al., (2020), stated that order to realize zero discharge of desulfurization wastewater, spray drying technology of desulfurization wastewater was used in 660MW unit of a power plant. Its principle was to use a rotary atomizer for atomization, and a part of hot flue gas was drawn from the SCR denitrification reactor and air preheater into the drying tower, the heat was used to evaporate the desulfurization wastewater in a spray drying tower.

The specific objectives of the study are the develop design equations for the process through the application of the principle of conservation of mass and energy, Solve the developed models using MATLAB and Carry out Sensitivity Analysis on the functional parameters of the reactors.

Appropriate steps was taken to achieve the research goal: From the foregoing several gaps are still needed to be filled from all various literatures cited so far in this work. While many of the researchers mainly focused on the modeling and simulation of desulfurization from gas feeds there is still the need to include a comprehensive design of the various equipment modeled and determine functional parameters like volume, height, diameter, residence time of process equipment used in the developed models. While most researchers limited their study to the use of a single fixed bed reactor, no one has yet considered the use of multiple fixed bed reactor in series to further reduce the Sulphur content in the gas stream before processing it. Finally, a case study of Indorama Petrochemical Ltd. has not been considered. But in all of these researches published, no researcher has yet to comparatively investigate the design and simulation of Hydrodesulphurization Unit for Natural Gas Treatment in an Ammonia Plant.

Hence, this study is aimed at investigating the design and simulation of Hydrodesulphurization Unit for Natural Gas Treatment in an Ammonia Plant.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

Materials for the study were Calculator, laptop, reference books (text books, & journals) and Physiochemical data of the plant (Indorama Petrochemical Company and shall consist of process flow diagrams of natural gas desulphurization unit made up of majorly absorption and reactor sections, operating conditions for feed streams and other utilities).

Methods

The development of the design equations for the absorber column and the fixed bed reactor for the hydro-desulphurization unit for natural gas in ammonia plant is carried out. The process flow diagram as shown in Figure 2.1 indicates the hydro-desulphurization unit which comprises of the absorber column where the H₂S/CH₄ gas mixture enters the absorber and the bottom and the absorbent (MDEA/H₂O) enters the column at the top counter currently for efficient absorption of the H₂S from the gas mixture. The absorbed gas together with the solvent enters the first fixed bed reactor for the removal or treatment of the waste mixtures to generate the solvent back and the pollutant (H₂S) separated from the waste mixture. Since the separation is not carried out completely, the second reactor is then used to completely separate the gas from the solvent. The method used for the development of the design models were based on the principle of material balance. The development of the models were also based on the works of Green et al., (2019) and Fogler, (2021) for the fixed bed reactor.

Design of the Absorber

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram for material Balance on the Absorber Column

For purity of the solvent,

$$X_2 = 0$$

$$Y = \frac{L_m}{G_m} X + Y_2 \quad (2.1)$$

where, G_m is determinant based on the actual or theoretical value. Any of this value which is smaller is chosen for the absorber design. The slope, m of the equilibrium line is given as,

$$y_e = \frac{Y_e}{1+Y_e} \quad (2.2)$$

$$x_e = \frac{X_e}{1+X_e} \quad (2.3)$$

$$V_w^* = \left[\frac{K_4 \rho_g (\rho_L - \rho_g)}{13.1 F_p \left(\frac{\mu_L}{\rho_L} \right)^{0.1}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.4)$$

where, F_p is the packing factor size for the type of packing used in the absorption, μ_L is the liquid viscosity of the absorbent.

The column area A_C is given or calculated in terms of V_w^* as:

$$A_C = \frac{G_m}{V_w^*} \quad (2.5)$$

Column diameter is obtained as:

$$D_C = \left(\frac{4A_C}{\pi} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.6)$$

The height of the absorber column is determined based on the overall gas transfer height, H_{OG} . This parameter is calculated based on the film transfer coefficients or film resistances for the liquid, K_{OL} and gas, K_{OG} . These parameters are linked using correlation from Onda *et al.*, (1968) as stated thus:

$$\frac{a_w}{a} = 1 - \exp \left\{ -1.45 \left(\frac{\sigma_C}{\sigma_L} \right)^{0.75} \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a\mu_L} \right)^{0.1} \left(\frac{L_w^* a}{\rho_L^2 g} \right)^{-0.05} \left(\frac{L_w^{*2}}{\rho_L \sigma_L a} \right)^{0.2} \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

where, a is actual area of packing per unit volume $\frac{m^2}{m^3}$, a_w is effective interfacial area of packing per unit volume, $\frac{m^2}{m^3}$, σ_C is critical surface tension for the particular packing material, σ_L is liquid surface tension, N/m and g in acceleration due to gravity, $\frac{9.81m}{s^2}$, L_w^* is liquid mass flow rate per unit column cross-sectional area $\frac{kg}{m^2.s}$.

The mass transfer coefficients, K_L and K_G are defined as,

$$K_L = 0.0051 \left(\frac{L_w^*}{a_w \mu_L} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\mu_L}{\rho_L D_L} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (adp)^{0.4} \left(\frac{\rho_L}{\mu_L g} \right)^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2.8)$$

where, K_L is overall liquid film mass transfer coefficient, $\frac{kmol}{m^2} \left(\frac{kmol}{m^3} \right)$, D_L is liquid diffusivity of the absorbent, $\frac{m^2}{s}$ and dp is the packing size, mm.

$$K_G = \frac{aD_V}{RT} K_5 \left(\frac{G_m^*}{a\mu_V} \right)^{0.7} \left(\frac{\mu_V}{\rho_V D_V} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} (adp)^{-2.0} \quad (2.9)$$

where, K_G is overall gas film mass transfer coefficient $\frac{kmol}{m^2.s.atm}$ or $\frac{kmol}{m^2} s \text{ bar}$, D_V is the vapour diffusivity of the absorbent, $\frac{m^2}{s}$ K_5 is 5.23 for packing sizes above 15mm and 2.00

for packing sizes below 15mm, G_m^* is gas mass flow rate per unit column cross-sectional area, $\frac{kg}{m^2.s}$ and μ_V is the vapour viscosity of the absorbent, Pa.s.

The film transfer unit heights are given by,

$$H_{OG} = \frac{G_m}{K_G a_w P} \quad (2.10)$$

$$H_{OL} = \frac{L_m}{K_L a_w C_t} \quad (2.11)$$

where, P is column operating pressure, atm or bar, C_t is total concentration $\frac{kmol}{m^3} \left(\frac{\rho_L}{M_{MDEA/water}} \right)$, $M_{MDEA/water}$ is molecular weight of the solvent (aqueous MDEA and water) and G_m and L_m are the molar flow rates per unit area cross-sectional flow for gas and liquid $\frac{kmol}{m^3} s$

H_{OG} can also be calculated from the following equations as,

$$H_G = \frac{G}{k_G a_w P} \quad (2.12)$$

$$H_L = \frac{L}{k_L a_w C_t} \quad (2.13)$$

where, K_G is gas film mass transfer coefficient $\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^2 \text{s atm}}$ or $\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^2} \text{s bar}$, k_L is liquid film mass transfer coefficient $\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^2} \left(\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3} \right)$

$$H_{OG} = H_G + \frac{m G_m}{L_m} H_L \quad (2.14)$$

The height of absorber column is this given as,

$$Z = N_{OG} H_{OG} \quad (2.15)$$

Including allowances, the total height, Z_T is given as,

$$Z_T = 1.3Z \quad (2.16)$$

Development of Design Equation for Fixed Bed Reactor

Design Assumptions

The following assumptions are necessary for the design of a packed bed reactor.

- The reactor is operated at unsteady state
- The composition of the reacting mixture is uniform only in the radial direction
- Balance can be made about a differential volume of reactor
- No conversion of reactant prior to inflow to the reactor volume.
- The process is non-isothermal

Volume of the Reactor

$$V = F_{AO} \int_{\alpha_{A0}}^{\alpha_A} \frac{d\alpha_A}{-r_A} \quad (2.17)$$

Weight of Catalyst

$$W = \rho F_{AO} \int_{\alpha_{A0}}^{\alpha_A} \frac{d\alpha_A}{-r_A} \quad (2.18)$$

Length of Reactor

$$L_R = \frac{4F_{AO}}{\pi D^2} \int_{X_{A0}}^{X_A} \frac{dX_A}{(-r_A)} \quad (2.19)$$

Space Time

$$\tau = C_{AO} \int_{\alpha_{A0}}^{\alpha_A} \frac{d\alpha_A}{-r_A} \quad (2.20)$$

Space Velocity

$$S_V = \frac{1}{\tau} \quad (2.21)$$

Heat Load

$$q = \frac{Q}{V_R} \quad (2.22)$$

where

$$Q = \Delta H_{rA} F_{A0} \alpha_A \quad (2.23)$$

Heat of Reaction

$$\Delta H_{rA} = \Delta H_{rA}^{o+} \int_{T_0}^T V \Delta C_p \Delta T \quad (2.24)$$

Mechanism and Kinetics

Thiols and sulphides react to form hydrogen sulphide and HC,

Mechanical Design Models for the Hydro-Desulphurization Plant

Cylindrical shell thickness

$$t_i = \frac{P_i D_i}{2fJ - P_i} + e \quad (2.26)$$

where, t_i is the thickness of the unit to be designed, J is 100% fully radiographed, and e is the corrosion allowance

Design of flat ends

$$t_p = C_p D_e \sqrt{\frac{P_i}{f}} + e \quad (2.27)$$

where, C_p is fully face gasket, 0.4, and D_e is the bolt circle diameter which is also the design diameter.

Doomed Head Design

Ellipsoidal head

$$t_i = \frac{P_i D_i}{2fJ - 0.2P_i} + e \quad (2.28)$$

Torispherical head

$$t_i = \frac{P_i D_i C_s}{2fJ + P_i(C_s - 0.2)} + e \quad (2.29)$$

where, C_s is stress concentration factor for torespherical head

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result obtained from the taking material balance around the entire absorber and reactors and solving them via MATLAB R2022a is presented in Tables 4.2 to 4.3 and Figures 4.1 to 4.4. The absorber has two inlets (inlet Gas and inlet solvent) streams and two outlet streams (Gas outlet and Liquid Outlet). The output from the absorber were sent to the two reactors configured to operate in series for the purpose of reducing the amount of H₂S to the barest minimum. The validation of the models results with plant is displaced in Table 4.1 and the sensitivity results of the volumetric flow rate effect on the functional parameters results of the reactors is shown in Figures 4.5 to 4.9.

Model Validation with Plant Data

Table 1: Comparison of Model Prediction with Plant Data

Stream Component	Plant Data	Model Prediction	% Deviation
CH ₄	0.8	0.83509	4.4
C ₂ H ₆	0.0288	0.029966	4
C ₃ H ₈	0.02	0.020763	3.815
C ₄ H ₁₀	0.01	0.010361	3.61
CO ₂	0.08	0.075478	5.65
O ₂	0.001	0.001045	4.5
N ₂	0.01	0.010446	4.46
H ₂ S	0.05	0.016641	66.7
He	0.0001	0.000104	4
Ne	0.0001	0.000105	5
MDEA	0	1.08E-06	0
H ₂ O	0	0	0

Table 2: Results obtained from Material Balance Result for the Absorption of H₂S from Natural Gas

Compon ent	Input 1		Input 2		Output 1		Output 2	
	S1 (mol)	S1 (mol/h)	S2 (mol)	S2 (mol/h)	S3 (mol)	S3 (mol/h)	S4 (mol)	S4 (mol/h)
CH ₄	0.8	7728.80	0	0.00	0.83509	7722.91	0.002136	2120.8 0
C ₂ H ₆	0.0288	278.24	0	0.00	0.029966	277.13	0.000413	76.35
C ₃ H ₈	0.02	193.22	0	0.00	0.020763	192.02	0.00045	53.02
C ₄ H ₁₀	0.01	96.61	0	0.00	0.010361	95.82	0.000296	26.51
CO ₂	0.08	772.88	0	0.00	0.075478	698.02	0.028234	212.08
O ₂	0.001	9.66	0	0.00	0.001045	9.66	7.46E-07	2.65
N ₂	0.01	96.61	0	0.00	0.010446	96.60	4.05E-06	26.51
H ₂ S	0.05	483.05	0	0.00	0.016641	153.90	0.124177	132.55
He	0.0001	0.97	0	0.00	0.000104	0.96	4.98E-07	0.27
Ne	0.0001	0.97	0	0.00	0.000105	0.97	0	0.27
MDEA	0	0.00	1	2238.0 0	1.08E-06	0.01	0.844289	0.00
H ₂ O	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
TOTAL	1	9661.00	1	2238.0 0	1	9248.00	1	2651.0 0

Table 3: Results obtained from Sizing and Specification of Absorber Unit

Parameter	Value	Unit
N _{OG}	6	
Cross Sectional Area	4.3704	m ²
Diameter	2.3589	m
H _{OG}	0.8431	m
Height (Z)	5.0586	m
Allowance for Liquid Distribution	1	m
Allowance for Liquid Redistribution	1	m
Total Height of Absorber	7.0586	m
Degree of Wetting	1.99 x 10 ⁻⁵	m ³ /m. sec
Pressure Drop	18.43	KN/m ²
Volume of Packing/plates	31	m ³

Table 3 shows the sizing/design result for fixed bed reactor 1, the sizing parameters considered includes diameter, cross sectional area, residence time, space velocity, reactor volume, and volumetric flow rate whose values are shown in Table 5.

Table 4: Results obtained from Sizing of Fixed Bed Reactor 1

Parameter	Value	Unit
Operating Temperature	60	°C
Operating Pressure	30	bar
Height of Reactor	6.74	m
Diameter	2.3	m
Cross sectional area	4.154	m ²
Residence time	8.3	mins
Space Velocity	0.12	min ⁻¹
Reactor Volume	249	m ³
Corrosion allowance	2	mm
Design Pressure Drop	0.7	bar
Material of Construction	Carbon Steel	
Volumetric flow Rate	30	m ³ /h

Table 4 shows the sizing/design result for fixed bed reactor 1, the sizing parameters considered includes diameter, cross sectional area, residence time, space velocity, reactor volume, and volumetric flow rate whose values are shown in Table 6.

Table 5: Results obtained from Sizing of Fixed Bed Reactor 2

Parameter	Value	Unit
Operating Temperature	400	°C
Operating Pressure	42	bar
Height of Reactor	6.74	m
Diameter	1.8	m
Cross sectional area	2.544	m ²
Residence time	4.3	mins
Space Velocity	0.2380	min ⁻¹
Reactor Volume	129	m ³
Corrosion allowance	2	mm
Design Pressure Drop	0.7	bar
Material of Construction	Carbon Steel	
Volumetric flow Rate	30	m ³ /h

Table 6: Results obtained from Mechanical Design for the Absorber Column

Parameter	Value	Unit
Operating Pressure	42	Bar
Design Pressure	45.1	Bar
Design Temperature	400	°C
Maximum Allowable Stress	92.39	N/mm ²
Cylindrical Section		
Thickness	18.9	mm
Corrosion Allowance	2	mm
Flat Head		
Thickness	45.44	mm
Corrosion Allowance	2	mm
Domed Head		
Standard Dished Head		
Crown radius	2.4	mm
Knuckle Radius	0.144	mm
Thickness	87	mm
Standard Ellipsoidal Head		
Thickness	18.88	mm

Table 7: Results obtained from Mechanical Design of a Fixed Bed Reactor 1

Parameter	Value	Unit
Operating Pressure	42	Bar
Design Pressure	45.1	Bar
Design Temperature	400	°C
Maximum Allowable Stress	153.46	N/mm ²
Cylindrical Section		
Thickness	90.8	Mm
Corrosion Allowance	2	Mm
Flat Head		
Thickness	117.3	mm
Corrosion Allowance	2	mm
Domed Head		
Standard Dished Head		
Crown radius	2.4	mm
Knuckle Radius	0.144	mm
Thickness	240.7	mm
Standard Ellipsoidal Head		
Thickness	90.7	mm

Table 8: Results obtained from Mechanical Design for Fixed Bed Reactor 2

Parameter	Value	Unit
Operating Pressure	42	Bar
Design Pressure	45.1	Bar
Design Temperature	400	°C
Maximum Allowable Stress	92.39	N/mm ²
Cylindrical Section		
thickness	22.9	mm
Corrosion Allowance	2	mm
Flat Head		
thickness	33	mm
Corrosion Allowance	2	mm
Domed Head		
Standard Dished Head		
Crown radius	2.4	mm
Knuckle Radius	0.144	mm
Thickness	66	mm
Standard Ellipsoidal Head		
Thickness	22.4	mm

Table 9: Results obtained from Costing of Absorber

Parameter	Value	Unit
Material of Construction	Stainless Steel	
Operating Pressure	17	Bar
Pressure Factor	1.1	
Material Factor	2.0	
Bare Cost	20,000	USD
Bare Cost	15,270,600	Naira
Purchased Cost	44,000	USD
Purchased Cost	33,595,320	Naira

Table 10: Results obtained from Costing of Fixed Bed Reactor 1

Parameter	Value	Unit
Material of Construction	Stainless Steel	
Operating Pressure	42	Bar
Pressure Factor	2.0	
Material Factor	2.0	
Bare Cost	30,000	USD
Bare Cost	34,350,000	Naira
Purchased Cost	120,000	USD
Purchased Cost	137,400,000	Naira

Table 11: Results obtained from Costing of Fixed Bed Reactor 2

Parameter	Value	Unit
Material of Construction	Stainless Steel	
Operating Pressure	42	Bar
Pressure Factor	2.0	
Material Factor	2.0	
Bare Cost	25,000	USD
Bare Cost	28,625,000	Naira
Purchased Cost	100,000	USD
Purchased Cost	114,500,000	Naira

Figure 3: Profile Plot of Mole Fraction Versus Reactor 1 Height

Figure 3 depicts the profile plot of mole fraction of reactants (CH₄ and H₂S) and desired product (ZnS) changing along the height of the reactor. A careful examination of Figure 3 reveals that the result obtained from simulation of developed model equations capable of predicting the mole fraction of reactants and products with reactor height is in agreement with trend. The first reactant component which is CH₄ started the reaction with an initial mole fraction of 0.42 and this value continued to decrease to a final mole fraction was 0.09.

Figure 4: Profile Plot of Conversion Versus Reactor 1 Height

Figure 4 shows the plot of conversion of reactants along the height of the fixed bed reactor, after the absorption of H₂S from the absorption unit, the unabsorbed H₂S is sent to the reactor section where ZnO which acts as the catalyst in this reaction reacts with H₂S to further reduce the concentration of H₂S. From the results obtained from the simulation, the conversion of ZnO rose from 0 to 78% while that of H₂S rose from 0 to 58%.

Figure 5: Profile Plot of Mole Fraction Versus Reactor 2 Height

Figure 5 depicts the profile plot of mole fraction of reactants (CH₄/ZnO and H₂S) and desired product (ZnS) changing along the height of the reactor. A careful examination of figure 4.3 reveals that the result obtained from simulation of developed model equations capable of predicting the mole fraction of reactants and products with reactor height is in agreement with trend in chemical reaction engineering where mole fraction of reactants decreases and mole fraction of products increases.

Figure 6: Profile Plot of Conversion Versus Reactor 2 Height

Figure 6 shows the plot of conversion of reactants along the height of the fixed bed reactor, after the absorption of H₂S from the absorption unit, the unabsorbed H₂S is sent to the fixed bed reaction section where ZnO which acts as the catalyst in this reaction reacts with H₂S to further reduce the concentration of H₂S. From the results obtained from the simulation, the conversion of ZnO rose from 0 to 55% while that of H₂S rose from 0 to 37%.

4. CONCLUSION

The simulation and design of 200 tons per year of desulphurization plant was carried out in this work. The design started by developing a process flow diagram of the plant which contains an absorber unit and two fixed bed reactors configured in series to reduce the amount of H₂S absorbed from the absorber unit to the barest minimum.

Design/sizing equations were also developed for each unit of the plant. The developed equations were then solved via MATLAB and Aspen HYSYS and the results obtained were presented in terms of material balance, energy balance, sizing/Design of equipment, mechanical design and equipment costing.

The design results for the absorber column and the reactors gave the diameters and heights of 2.36m and 5.06m; 2.3m and 6.74m; and 1.8m and 6.74m respectively. It was observed that the pressure drop of the fixed bed reactors were 0.7bar.

It was carefully observed that in all cases, all variables had a direct relationship with the volumetric flow rate except for residence time which had an inverse relationship with volumetric flow rate.

REFERENCES

- Abdel-Aal, K. & Aggour, M. (2003) *Petroleum and Gas Field Processing*. New York: CRC Press.
- Adschiri T, Shibata R, Sato T, Watanabe M, & Arai K (2013) Catalytic hydrodesulphurization of dibenzothiophene through partial oxidation and a water-gas shift reaction in supercritical water. *Ind Eng Chem Res.*, 37:2634–2638.

- Agarwal P., & Sharma D.K. (2010) Comparative studies on the bio-desulfurization of crude oil with other desulfurization techniques and deep desulfurization through integrated processes. *Energy Fuels*, 24:518–524.
- Apoorva, A., Sajan, S., Abhishek, S.N., Rahul, S., & Chetan, C. (2018). Desulphurization of Crude Oil. *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 7(2), 242-251.
- Aysar, T.J. (2023). *Kinetic Modeling Simulation and Optimal Operation of Trickle Bed Reactor for Hydrotreating of Crude Oil*. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/10454/5363>.
- Bakhshi, A.A., & Ebrahim, H.A. (2021). Modeling and Multi-Objective Optimization of a Packed Bed Reactor for Sulphur Dioxide Removal by Magnesium Oxide Using Non- Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II. *Journal of Chemical and Biochemical Engineering*, 35(3), 251-256.
- Carroll, J. (2009) *Natural Gas Hydrates: A Guide for Engineers*. Oxford: Gulf Professional Publishing.
- Dadashvand, R., Mollahosseini, A., Alimorad, M., & Ramezani, M. (2020). Natural Gas Condensate Desulphurization via Polyacrylonitrile/Ag Nanocomposite Nanofibers: Optimization and Kinetics/Isotherm Studies. *Journal of Science of Islamic Republic of Iran*, 31(4), 305-319.
- Dushyant, S., Todd, H.G., & David, A.B. (2004, Nov 7-12). *Natural Gas Odorants Desulphurization* [Paper Presentation]. AIChE Annual National Meeting, Texas, United States.
- Fogler, H. S. (2021). *Elements of Chemical Reaction Engineering*, (3rd edition), Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi.
- Francis, S. (2018) *Oilfield Processing of Petroleum: Natural Gas*. Tulsa: PennWell.
- Goodhead, T.O & Abowei, M.F.N. (2014). Design of Isothermal Plug Flow Reactor adsorption tower for sulfur trioxide hydration using Vanadium catalyst. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Modern Energy*, 2(9), 1-15.
- Green, D. W. & Southard, M. Z. (2019). *Perry's Chemical Engineering Handbook*, (9th edition), McGraw Hill, New York, pp. 33-89
- Javad, A.K., & Elhameh, N. (2016). Simulation of Hydrodesulfurization Unit for Natural Gas Condensate with High Sulphur Content. *Applied Petrochemical Research*, 6, 25-34.
- Javadli, R., De-Klerk, A. (2012). Desulfurization of Heavy Oil. *Applied Petrochemical Research*, 1, 3-19.
- Justyna, K., & Wojciech, B. (2016). Adsorbents used for Biogas Desulfurization in the Adsorption Process. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 25(1), 37-43.
- Kohl, L. & Rosenfeld, A. (2015) *Gas purification*. Oxford: Gulf Professional Publishing.
- Maddox, R. (2010) *Gas conditioning and processing: gas and liquid sweetening*. Oklahoma: Campbell petroleum.
- Maya (2012) Removal of CO₂ and N₂ from natural gas: A review of conventional and emerging process technologies. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering* 94-106
- Melahn, P. (2010). Method for Removing Hydrogen Sulphide from Sour Gas and Converting it to Hydrogen and Sulphuric Acid. [Doctoral Thesis, Stanford University].
- Mokhatab, S., Poe, W. & Speigh, J. (2006). *Handbook of natural gas transmission and processing*. Texas: Gulf Publishing Co.
- Nawaree, S. (2009). Systematic Design Procedures for Natural Gas Desulphurization [Project Dissertation, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS].

- Nima, N., & Ehsan, H.B. (2021). Modeling of the Hydrodesulphurization Process of Natural Gas Condensates. *International Journal of New Chemistry*, 9(4), 309-320.
- Peyman, M., Mohammad, T.S., Hamid, G., & Saeed, S. (2012). Two-Dimensional Dynamic Modeling of Hydrodesulphurization Reactor. *Journal of Petroleum Science Research*, 1(2), 32-35.
- Ramiar, S.V., & Matthaus, U.B. (2019). Removal of Hydrogen Sulphide with Metal Oxides in packed Bed Reactors: A Review from Modeling Perspective with Practical Implications. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(1), 1-24.
- Ray, S., & Cavin, T. (2013). *Chemical Engineering Design Volume 6*, New York, USA: Elsevier.
- Ribwar, A., & Sebastine, I. (2013). Desulphurization of Natural Gas by Using Adsorption Method: A Case Study of Lennox Gas Field. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(1), 150-165.
- Ribwar, A., Ibtisam, K., & Jagar, A. (2015). Natural Gas Desulphurization Process by MEA Amine: The Preferable Engineering Design Procedure. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, 28(5), 214-218.
- Richardson, J.F., Harker, J.H., & Backhurst, J.R. (2011). *Chemical Engineering: Particle Technology and Separation Processes Volume 2* (5th Ed). New York, USA: Elsevier.
- Sinnott, R. & Towler, G. (2009). Chemical engineering design principles, practice and economics of plant and process design, 6(5). California, Elsevier.
- Stewart, M. and Arnold, K. (2011) *Gas Sweetening and Processing Field Manual*. Waltham: Gulf professional publishing.
- Suthida, A., Worasorn, P., Dang, S., Yaneeporn, P., & Amornchai, A. (2008). Modeling of an Industrial Fixed Bed Reactor Based on Lumped Kinetic Models for Hydrogenation of Pyrolysis Gasoline. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 14, 771-778.
- Ujile, A.A. (2014). *Chemical Engineering Unit Operations: Synthesis and Basic Design Calculations*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Bomm Prints.
- Zhang, S., Wang, R., Tang, G., & Dai, Y. (2020). Application and Performance Evaluation of Desulphurization Waste Water Spray Drying Technology. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202014302029>.
- Zhiguo, W., Fei, W., Yali, Z., & Bengang, G. (2019). Method of Desulfurization Process Selection Based on Improved Fuzzy Comprehensive Evaluation: A Case Study of papermaking Desulfurization in China. *Processes*, 7, 446-560.